

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA)

Exploring Multimorbidity and Patterns of
Long-term Conditions in England using
Open Prescription and Primary Care Data

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Multimorbidity (the presence of ≥ 2 long-term health conditions in an individual) is increasing as a consequence of population ageing and improved medical care [1]. Multimorbidity is associated with a range of adverse health states and outcomes, including polypharmacy (the concurrent use of multiple medications) [2], frailty [3], dependency [4], poor quality of life [5], and premature mortality [6]. Developing a greater understanding of multimorbidity and how it may be treated has been identified as a major strategic priority [7, 8]. At present, limited data exist to describe longitudinal trends in the geospatial distribution of multimorbidity.

Multimorbidity and polypharmacy are overlapping concepts: the greater the number of conditions with which a person has been diagnosed, the more medications they are likely to be prescribed. As such, it stands to reason that prescribing patterns at the population level can tell us a great deal about the multimorbidity state of the underlying population. Using open prescribing data, we explored the relationship between multimorbidity and the prescribing patterns of common medications used in the treatment of long-term conditions (LTCs) in England. This work was conducted as part of a Data Study Group, led by Dr Jonathan Batty (Leeds Institute of Data Analytics) and took place over the course of one week.

1.2 Data overview

The challenge used area-based estimates of multimorbidity available at the 2011 electoral ward level. These were made available to Public Health England (PHE) by Barnett et al. [9]. Multimorbidity prevalence estimates (≥ 2 long-term conditions), stratified by age, sex and socioeconomic deprivation status, were available for all 7,689 2011 electoral wards (reflecting $n = 53.1$ million people).

Monthly medication prescribing data at the GP surgery level are routinely released by NHS Digital and available openly via the Practice Level Prescribing Dataset (PLPD; 2011-2013) [10] and the English Prescribing Dataset (EPD; 2014-2022) [11]. These prescribing data are coded using the British National Formulary (BNF) system. The BNF contains all medicines available within the National Health Service and is updated periodically.

These data enabled the exploration of area-based associations between multimorbidity prevalence and prescribing patterns in 2011, in addition to enabling prescription patterns to be tracked over time. All data was aggregated at the GP surgery or electoral ward level; no identifiable or individual-level data were used during this challenge.

1.3 Objectives

This challenge aimed to:

- Identify the utility of open prescribing data in determining geospatial multimorbidity patterns.
- Identify the association between historic area-based multimorbidity prevalence and medication prescribing patterns.
- Explore other determinants of multimorbidity in England, based on linked GP-level and census-derived, area-based data.
- Devise and evaluate an appropriate model of area-based multimorbidity prevalence, using the predictors identified during exploratory data analysis.
- Explore whether changes in prescribing patterns may be used to track trends in multimorbidity at an area-based level, over time.

1.4 Approach

Following the aggregation of monthly prescribing data at the GP surgery level to annual counts by 2011 electoral wards, exploratory data analyses focused on identifying predictors of area-based multimorbidity prevalence. This included exploration of socio-demographic factors, including the population structure of an electoral ward (by age group, sex and socioeconomic status) in addition to the association of marginal prescribing patterns (*e.g.* total number and cost of medication items prescribed within a geographic area). Subsequently, a hierarchical Bayesian linear modelling approach was used to robustly evaluate the association of socio-demographic factors with multimorbidity prevalence using an *a priori* defined hierarchical model.

Two interpretable forms of supervised machine learning techniques were used to identify specific prescribing patterns associated with multimorbidity prevalence: elastic net linear regression, and random forests regression. Cross-validation was used to: (i) evaluate the performance of each modelling strategy, (ii) identify the most appropriate geographic level for modelling (local authority vs. electoral ward area) (iii) identify the most appropriate grouping of medications (*e.g.*, BNF chapter vs. sub-chapter level), and (iv) identify the most suitable hyperparameters for variable selection during modelling.

Finally, exploratory time-series analysis was performed to evaluate the feasibility of using longitudinal prescribing data to predict changes in multimorbidity prevalence over time. Specific electoral wards were identified to illustrate where our approach could work well, in addition to demonstrating properties of these area-based data that may preclude meaningful forecasting in some cases.

1.5 Conclusions

We found that areas with an older average age, a greater proportion of women and greater level of socioeconomic deprivation had a greater prevalence of multimorbidity, in line with previous analyses conducted with individual-level healthcare data [9]. The strongest determinant of multimorbidity prevalence was the age structure of the population. Deprivation status was best modelled as an interaction term, leading to effect measure modification across strata of age.

The inclusion of the prescribing data in both elastic net and random forest regression-based models were evaluated. Overall, elastic net linear regression models consistently outperformed random forest models, based on a number of model fit metrics. Different models were examined that included different granularity of prescription data – from the number and cost of prescriptions made at a high-level (such as 2-digit BNF chapter codes, *e.g.* '02: Cardiovascular System'), to a more precise coding level (such as 6-digit BNF drug class codes, *e.g.* '020505: Renin-angiotensin System Drugs').

In addition to the aforementioned predictors of multimorbidity (age, sex and deprivation), models that included 6-digit BNF codes outperformed those including less precise medication coding. This model identified a number of agents that were significantly positively associated with multimorbidity prevalence (including nitrates, calcium-channel blockers and other antianginal drugs) and agents that were significantly negatively associated with multimorbidity prevalence (combined hormonal contraceptives and emergency allergy drugs).

1.6 Limitations

This work has a number of important limitations. Firstly, the cross-sectional nature of this analysis limits inference regarding the directionality of the associations identified. Conclusions drawn from these analyses relate only to geographical areas and not to individuals (ecological fallacy).

Secondly, the application of our models in forecasting area-based changes in multimorbidity using socio-demographic and prescribing trend data were limited by the geospatial nature of the multimorbidity prevalence dataset. Multimorbidity prevalence data were available at ward level, estimated for a single year (2011). Over time, ward boundaries (and the subsequent reporting of small area-based population statistics) have changed markedly, making comparisons over time challenging.

Finally, based on the available data, we made the strong assumption that all prescribing activity by a GP surgery was for patients living in that ward. This is very unlikely to be the case; some wards have multiple GP surgeries, whereas peripheral wards have none. As such, a more complex methodology of

apportioning prescriptions by registered GP population may produce more robust results. Unfortunately, data enabling such an analytic approach was not routinely made available in 2011.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

Further work should seek to use routinely-collected healthcare data to perform individual-level ascertainment of multimorbidity status within a population, in order to generate robust, longitudinal, area-based estimates of multimorbidity prevalence. The unit of geography used in such an analysis should be based on consistently defined Output Areas (OAs), which would overcome some of the limitations of the ward-based estimates used in this challenge.

Overall, a greater understanding of the geospatial distribution of multimorbidity may enable more equitable targeting of resources, enabling multimorbidity-focused prevention and intervention measures to be delivered to regions in which the burden of multimorbidity is greatest.

2 Data Overview

2.1 Ward-level multimorbidity prevalence data

Estimates of the prevalence of multimorbidity at the 2011 (Census-based) electoral ward level were published in 2018 by Public Health England (PHE). These estimates were based on observed prevalence data from Barnett et al. [9]. Barnett et al. defined multimorbidity as the presence of ≥ 2 long-term health conditions in an individual and reported its prevalence by sex, age group and decile of socioeconomic deprivation (using the 1991 Carstairs Index [12]). In total, 40 long-term conditions were considered in the definition of multimorbidity, with each condition having a prevalence in the overall population that ranged from 0.1 to 13.4% (Table 1). These included core conditions included in the Quality Outcomes Framework (QOF) – a key part of performance-based payment for general practitioners (GPs) in the United Kingdom (UK).

These data enabled the estimation of the prevalence of multimorbidity. Wards were defined as those following the May 2011 boundary review in England. Both crude and age- and sex-standardised multimorbidity prevalence data are plotted at 2011 ward level in Figure 1. In total, data were available for all 7,689 2011 electoral wards (reflecting $n = 53.1$ million people) in England.

2.2 Prescription data

The Practice Level Prescribing Dataset (PLPD) contains monthly data on all prescriptions issued by General Practitioner (GP) practices in England [10]. This includes prescriptions of medicines, dressings and appliances made by GPs and other medical professionals (including prescribing nurses and pharmacists) attached to practices. Data are also available for prescriptions issued in England but dispensed in Wales, Scotland, Guernsey, Alderney, Jersey, and the Isle of Man.

In a given month, records are only released for a given GP surgery for items prescribed and dispensed. No record is generated for a given British National Formulary (BNF) code unless a GP practice prescribes at least one item.

The PLPD data includes:

- The number of units (total prescriptions made containing that formulation, regardless of quantity),
- The total quantity (the total amount of the preparation prescribed),
- The net ingredient cost (NIC) and actual cost for each BNF code.

The NIC represents the total prescription cost based on wholesale prices whilst the actual cost allows for national average discounts and payments made to dispensers. The PLPD was superseded from January 2014 by the

Figure 1: Multimorbidity prevalence mapped at the 2011 ward level

(a) Crude prevalence of multimorbidity in England, 2011

(b) Age and sex-standardised prevalence of multimorbidity in England, 2011

Table 1: List of conditions contributing to the definition of multimorbidity and their prevalence, as specified by Barnett et al. [9].

Condition	Type	2011 prevalence (%)
Hypertension	Physical	13.4
Depression	Mental	8.2
Painful condition	Physical	6.0
Coronary heart disease	Physical	4.7
Treated dyspepsia	Physical	4.5
Diabetes	Physical	4.3
Thyroid disorders	Physical	4.1
Rheumatoid arthritis	Physical	3.4
Hearing loss	Physical	3.4
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Physical	3.2
Anxiety & other neurotic, stress related disorders	Mental	3.2
Irritable bowel syndrome	Physical	3.0
New diagnosis of cancer in last five years	Physical	2.5
Alcohol problems	Mental	2.4
Other psychoactive substance misuse	Mental	2.4
Treated constipation	Physical	2.2
Stroke & transient ischaemic attack	Physical	2.1
Chronic kidney disease	Physical	1.9
Diverticular disease of intestine	Physical	1.9
Atrial fibrillation	Physical	1.4
Peripheral vascular disease	Physical	1.3
Heart failure	Physical	1.1
Prostate disorders	Physical	0.9
Glaucoma	Physical	0.9
Epilepsy (currently treated)	Physical	0.8
Dementia	Mental	0.7
Schizophrenia or bipolar disorder	Mental	0.7
Psoriasis or eczema	Physical	0.7
Inflammatory bowel disease	Physical	0.6
Migraine	Physical	0.6
Blindness & low vision	Physical	0.5
Chronic sinusitis	Physical	0.5
Learning disability	Mental	0.3
Anorexia or bulimia	Mental	0.3
Bronchiectasis	Physical	0.2
Parkinson's disease	Physical	0.2
Multiple sclerosis	Physical	0.2
Viral Hepatitis	Physical	0.1
Chronic liver disease	Physical	0.1

English Prescribing Dataset (EPD) [11], which has a somewhat simpler and more consistent data schema. Prescriptions are coded using BNF in line with the PLPD and broadly the same data fields were provided. Full documentation

regarding the EPD is provided by the NHS Business Services Authority [13].

Of note, the PLPD and EPD data routinely exclude:

- Prescriptions issued outside of England (*i.e.*, Wales, Scotland, Guernsey, Alderney, Jersey, and the Isle of Man).
- Items that were not dispensed or were disallowed, including prescriptions not collected by an individual, or cancelled due to error.
- Prescriptions prescribed and dispensed in prisons, or in secondary or tertiary care (although in general, GPs assume responsibility for issuing repeat prescriptions for the management of chronic conditions).
- Private prescriptions.

For each month of PLPD data, a series of relational `.csv` files were released (containing data on prescriptions issued, GP practices and medication formulations). These were linked by a common GP surgery identifier. For each month of EPD data, a single file was released which resembles the result of merging the PLPD files based on the GP practice identifier.

2.3 Population data

The Office for National Statistics (ONS) provided a number of population estimate publications relevant to this challenge, including mid-year, ward-level population estimates [14]. These contained population estimates for all electoral wards in England and Wales from mid-2001 to mid-2020, excluding 18 wards that did not meet minimum population requirements (40 households, with 100 residents at the 2011 Census). These data are based on 31 December 2020 boundaries, with population estimates for each year adjusted to reflect 2020 wards, rather than the ward boundaries in effect at the time. There are 8,053 wards in the dataset.

Electoral ward `shapefiles` were obtained from the ONS Open Geography Portal to support the aggregation of GP surgeries to electoral wards and plotting geospatial data [15]. The ONS publishes these data in a variety of formats. The National Statistics Postcode Lookup (available from the ONS Open Geography Portal) was used to assign postcodes to 2011 wards.

2.4 Data processing

A combination of both R (version 4.2.1) and Python (version Python 3.11.2) were used for data processing.

2.4.1 The Public Health England multimorbidity data

The PHE multimorbidity prevalence data contained complete data for 2011 (Census-based) electoral wards. No other pre-processing of this dataset was required.

2.4.2 Prescription data

Although the PLPD and EPD contain similar data, each has a specific format and schema. As such, the prescribing data for 2011 - 2013 (PLPD) and for 2014 onwards (EPD) were pre-processed separately. Briefly, the raw PLPD data for each month were downloaded as `.zip` files, extracted and merged. The PLPD field names were renamed and the data reformatted to yield a single `.csv` file in line with the format of the EPD data.

The EPD data may be queried through an application programming interface (API), which accepts SQL queries. The EPD database holds prescription data in separate tables for each calendar year. The API was used to request a subset of columns for each year as an alternative to downloading all raw data. However, the API returned links to `.csv` files held in a public Google Cloud storage bucket if the number of results were large. We attempted to use these links to download the data however it was found that the SQL API was unsuitable for large requests, potentially due to rate limiting. It remains an efficient approach for simple queries returning a smaller set of results (for example, the top 5 prescriptions by cost, filtered by specific criteria). As such, the raw `.csv` file for each calendar month of EPD data was therefore downloaded from the EPD website as a `.zip` file and extracted.

The total combined (PLPD and EPD) prescribing dataset exceeded 1Tb in size. Therefore, a memory efficient approach was developed in R to iterate through the zipped files, extract the `.csv`, carry out initial processing (see below), append the processed data to a list and delete the `.csv` file before moving to the next file. The resultant processed dataset was relatively small (~4Gb for the full 12 year combined dataset) and could therefore easily be held in memory.

A common series of pre-processing steps were undertaken for the combined prescribing data:

- The `PRACTICE`, `POSTCODE`, `BNF_CODE`, `ITEMS`, `QUANTITY`, `NIC` and `ACTUAL_COST` columns were extracted.
- Postcodes were mapped to census wards using the ONS National Statistics Postcode Lookup.
- Rows with missing data were dropped and the sum of the `ITEMS`, `QUANTITY`, `NIC` and `ACTUAL_COST` columns were grouped by ward and calendar year.

- String methods were used to collapse the original 15-digit BNF code into less granular levels (i.e. 2-, 4-and 6-digits).

2.4.3 ONS population data

The ONS Ward-level Population Estimates Data (the “ONS population dataset”) was preprocessed to remove data that was not relevant to this study. This included wards not in England and years not within the 2011 - 2020 period. For each remaining ward and calendar year, the following were calculated:

- Total female population
- Female proportion of ward population
- Average female age
- Total male population
- Average male age
- Average age

The 2011 Carstairs Index deprivation decile for each ward was added from the PHE dataset. The deprivation decile calculated based on 2011 data was applied to all subsequent years (2011 - 2020). Although other deprivation measures are available at ward level after 2011, initial inspection demonstrated deprivation status to remain fairly constant over the study period.

2.4.4 The analytical dataset

The PHE multimorbidity, PLPD, EPD prescribing and ONS population statistic datasets were merged by ward identifier prior to modelling. To enable preliminary evaluation of methods, wards were also aggregated to a higher geographical level (Local Authority District [LAD], $n = 328$). As an LAD is made up of a number of wards, all the independent variables (features) at LAD level were generated by summing up data for each constituent ward. Multimorbidity prevalence at the LAD level was computed by dividing the number of people with multimorbidity in the LAD by its total population.

Mean imputation of missing age data was performed due to the time and computational restraints imposed by the Data Study Group challenge. However, we recognise that this is a biased approach to handling missing data and more suitable multiple imputation methods should be considered in future work. In the event of missing deprivation data, the most recently available deprivation decile was carried forward. Wards without prescribing data (*i.e.* due to the lack of a GP surgery) were dropped.

2.5 Data quality issues

2.5.1 Difference between PLPD and EPD definitions

The definition of QUANTITY varied between the PLPD and EPD datasets. For the PLPD, it represented the total quantity prescribed for each drug e.g. the total number of tablets prescribed across all prescriptions of the drug. For the EPD, it presented the typical quantity in one prescription of each drug. A TOTAL_QUANTITY field was provided that appeared to be equivalent to PLPD QUANTITY.

2.5.2 Quantity field

The recorded quantity of a medication prescribed depends on the specific formulation. For example, for a medication in tablet form, the quantity reflects the number of tablets prescribed. For a medication in liquid form, the quantity reflects the number of millilitres prescribed. As such, the quantity of medication prescribed exists on vastly different scales, dependent on the specific formulation. There is no straightforward lookup available to convert from quantity to a formulation-invariant measure (such as dose in milligrams) across different preparations of the same medication. For this reason, our analysis focused on the number of prescriptions and the cost of the agent, rather than the absolute quantity prescribed.

2.5.3 Geospatial distribution of GP surgeries and prescribing data

In total, there were 7,689 wards in England in 2011 with multimorbidity prevalence; only 4,571 wards had prescription data. Only wards representing the intersection of those with both multimorbidity and prescribing data (4,381 wards) could therefore be used for modelling.

There were 3,308 wards without prescription data. As prescriptions are related to the practice in which they were prescribed, not the patient's home address, it was expected that wards without a GP practice would be without prescription data. Indeed, wards without prescription data had on average half the population compared to wards with prescription data (mean population for those with vs without: 4,556 vs 8,681 people). This may have meant that wards near to those without prescription data have inflated prescription records (as a result of prescribing to patients who did not contribute to the population count or morbidity prevalence of the ward).

There were 190 wards with prescription data that did not have multimorbidity prevalence data. These corresponded to wards which ceased to exist in May 2011, and were considered in the 2011 prescription data cut (which appears to use wards from March 2011) but not in the 2011 census. This issue was eventually addressed by geocoding the centroid of postcodes from GP surgeries contributing to the prescription data to a 2011 ward boundary

shapefile. However, as the complete mapping for these wards came towards the end of the project, and considering they made up a small proportion of total wards, these were not used in the analysis.

We explored the use of aggregating wards into LADs (the next geographical 'level up') to overcome the limitation of wards without data. LADs collapse wards into larger units of area and the multimorbidity and prescription counts are simply summed for all included wards. Wards with missing data contribute zero and we assumed that wards without representation in either dataset have their patients taken into account in nearby wards, and that these belong to the same local authority districts. However, the use of LADs reduced the 2011 dataset to ~300 datapoints, leading to many more predictors than observations (the so-called $p > n$ problem) and limiting the number of covariates that could be included in the multimorbidity prevalence prediction model. In order to model multimorbidity using granular prescribing data (i.e. 4- or 6-digits) ward-level data were used.

2.5.4 Change in ward boundaries over time

Over time, the boundaries used to define wards were altered. Wards were merged, split, expanded or reduced to include a different geographical area. Thus, the wards used to model multimorbidity in 2011 were different to the wards used for prescription data for 2012 onwards. Theoretically, the multimorbidity prevalence of such "new wards" wards could be predicted, given the existence of known ward-specific predictors. However, it is unusual for such data to be made available on an annual basis; census-based estimates are only available every 10 years.

2.6 Data summary

2.6.1 Electoral wards

Overall, 3,308 wards for which there was both multimorbidity prevalence and prescribing data were used in the primary analysis. A summary of these wards is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: A summary of wards used in the primary analysis

Measure	Min	Q1	Median	Mean	Q3	Max
Multimorbidity prevalence	0.05	0.21	0.24	0.24	0.26	0.51
Female (proportion)	0.33	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.56
Age (mean)	23.1	36.9	40.1	39.9	43.0	62.4
Deprivation decile	1	3	6	5.9	9	10
Total population	226	4,928	7,386	8,682	11,889	36,227

2.6.2 BNF chapters

Prescriptions were coded in a hierarchical manner using 15-digit British National Formulary (BNF) codes, each of which represents a specific preparation of a medication. The first two digits represent the chapter of the BNF in which the medication is found (which broadly correspond to body systems, *e.g.*, “02 – Cardiovascular System”).

The subsequent two digits correspond to the BNF section (*e.g.*, “0205 - drugs for hypertension and heart failure”). The next two digits correspond to BNF paragraph (*e.g.*, “020504: Alpha-adrenoceptor blocking drugs”) and are followed by more digits that capture the BNF sub-paragraph, chemical substance, produce, strength and formulation. For example, 040702040BIACAM refers to “Trandorec XL Tablets 300 mg”. More digits confer a finer level of granularity. Full-granularity is both methodologically difficult to account for (there were 24,069 distinct BNF codes in the 2011 data, prescribed at least once) and lacks clinical relevance as a predictor of multimorbidity (*e.g.* whether a drug is in generic form or not).

In our analysis, BNF codes were considered up to 6-digit granularity. The number of distinct BNF codes in the 2011 data (prescribed at least once by at least one ward) were: 728 at 6-digit level, 205 at 4-digit level, and 21 at 2-digit level. Codes were removed if at least 50% of wards issued no prescriptions in the year. This removed 431 codes at the 6-digit level, 68 codes at the 4-digit level, and 1 at the 2-digit level (BNF Chapter 18 - preparations used in diagnosis, which are expected to be infrequently prescribed in primary care settings).

2.6.3 Measures of prescription burden: number of items, quantity, net ingredient and actual cost

For each BNF code, four complementary measures of prescription burden exist: items (number of prescriptions), quantity (number of units prescribed, such as tablets or millilitres), NIC and actual cost. The limitations of each measure, and how others help to minimise these, are summarised below.

- **Items:** An item represents a single prescription (for any quantity of medication) and is therefore independent of formulation. However, two prescriptions of varying sizes will contribute equally towards item count. For example, a pack of 5 tablets and a pack of 30 tablets will each correspond to 1 item, meaning that items will be inflated depending on how regularly prescriptions are made, which may vary by person and disease.
- **Quantity:** The units used to measure quantity depend on formulation. For example, the quantity of a tablet medication is number of tablets prescribed, whereas the quantity of a liquid is the number of millilitres

prescribed. As BNF codes at the 6-digit level include drugs of different formulations, the measures of quantity used were an aggregated measure of different units. As nearly all drugs in tablet form have a liquid equivalent, this may cause difficulties with interpretation. Further, for two drugs of similar dosage, medications in liquid form will correspond to a larger quantity compared to tablets, and quantity will therefore be inflated depending on the proportion of patients on different formulations. This potentially causes difficulties from a modelling point of view (if proportion of liquid users varies by ward/LAD, or if formulation popularity changes over time). The need for liquids medications is greater at the extremes of age: an area with more children or older people may be associated with a greater use of liquid medication. A solution would be to separate medications by formulation, but dimensionality problems arise, especially as there are several formulations other than tablet/liquid (e.g. bag, cigarette, cm, cup, device, insert). There is no immediate lookup to identify only tablet medications and as such, any manual sorting of medications by formulation was outwith the scope of this DSG.

- **Cost:** Analysing the cost of a prescription may help counteract the limitations above, as the expectation is that this should be roughly in proportion with both quantity and dose. For example, the cost of a pack of 20 tablets is expected to be roughly in proportion to the cost of a pack of 40 tablets. The limitation here is that cost of medications may depend on specific arrangements, such as discounts for large purchases. The cost for the same product may therefore depend on geography (e.g. by commissioning group), as well as demographics and disease-profiles within an area (e.g. number of people requiring a given medication).
- **Net Ingredient Cost (NIC):** NIC represents ingredient cost only and therefore overcomes the limitations of using the actual cost. However, NIC may not correlate well with multimorbidity burden. For example, there exist highly expensive medications which are used infrequently, meaning a single prescription for a single patient may contribute heavily to overall prescription cost for a given area.

As all medication quantifiers are associated with their own limitations, all four were considered as candidates during the modelling process. It was noted during exploratory data analysis that the correlation between NIC and actual cost was very high, as demonstrated in [Figure 2](#).

2.7 Data assumptions

The following assumptions were made regarding during this project:

- The socioeconomic deprivation status of an area does not change over time (*i.e.* within a decade). This assumption was evaluated by inspecting

Figure 2: Scatter plot matrix of prescription variables, at the BNF chapter level (each data point represents one BNF chapter for each ward). Labels: valuecost - actual cost, valuequantity - quantity, valueitems - items and valuenic - NIC.

available ward-level ONS deprivation data (deciles of 2015 and 2019 Index of Multiple Deprivation [IMD] score). The correlation between area-level IMD deciles in 2015 and 2019 was 0.981, in support of this assumption. As such, the deprivation decile value from 2011 was therefore used for 2012 - 2020.

- Prescriptions are made from a GP surgery within a given ward to people residing within the same ward. Although NHS Digital now publish small area level GP surgery registration data, this was not available for the period in question.
- We assume non-informative missingness for wards without either multimorbidity or prescription data (which cannot be included in the present analysis), though this may not have been met in reality.

3 Exploratory Data Analysis and Data Visualisation

In order to understand how to best use the data available to model multimorbidity, it was necessary to first undertake exploratory data analysis (EDA) in order to understand how to best summarise, visualise, and make sense of the data.

3.1 2011 wards with available prescribing data

Wards only had prescribing data available if they contained a GP surgery that prescribed medications in 2011. The location of GP surgeries in England and wards with available prescription data are shown below in Figure 3.

The wards without prescription data were inspected to assess how the exclusion of these wards may affect modelling. The wards with missing prescription data had a non-significantly higher prevalence of multimorbidity, compared to those without missing data (mean 0.237 vs. 0.243, respectively). The availability of prescription data also appears to be related to the deprivation of a ward, as shown in Figure 4b.

3.2 Distribution of prescription data

We inspected the distribution of prescription items, quantity, cost and quantity for each BNF chapter, across 2011 wards. Box plots were used to visualise the data and identify statistical outlier values (Figure 5). Removal of the outliers allowed for a better inspection of the distribution of prescription data across wards (Figure 6). Removal of the outliers allows for a better inspection of the distribution of prescription volume measures. Note that outlier values *were* retained in all subsequent modelling stages.

Unsurprisingly, given the high degree of correlation, the cost and NIC graphs look similar. The chapters which have a relatively high quantity or items prescribed but not cost may contain cheaper (or a greater proportion of *generic*) medications.

3.3 Uni- and bivariate associations of multimorbidity prevalence

EDA helped us to identify univariate and bivariate determinants of multimorbidity prevalence, enabling decisions to be made about which variables should be included in models, and whether data transformations may have been required.

Firstly, we noted the multimorbidity prevalence had an approximately normal distribution across the wards for which there were both multimorbidity and

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of prescription data

(a) 2011 GP surgeries (red dots)

(b) 2011 wards with prescribing data (shaded)

Figure 4: Exploring patterns of missingness in the data

(a) Wards with and without prescription data

(b) Wards with and without deprivation data

Figure 5: Distribution of prescription data by ward (2011)

prevalence data (Figure 7).

Secondly, we noted a clear relationship between the proportion of people in older age categories with a ward and the prevalence of multimorbidity at the ward level (Figure 8a). Contrary to our expectation, however, we were surprised to note that as a standalone predictor, deprivation appeared to have no association with multimorbidity prevalence at the ward level (8b).

However, we hypothesised that:

- Deprivation and age are interdependent: areas of high deprivation have a higher mortality rate than affluent areas, meaning fewer people make it to old age [16]. At the same time, areas of high deprivation have higher birth rates than affluent areas [17, 18].
- Deprivation and multimorbidity are interdependent: Despite the higher mortality rate for patients living in deprived areas, patients still spend

Figure 6: Summary of prescription data per head by BNF chapter, outliers removed

approximately twice as many years in poor health prior to death than those in affluent areas. [19] Barnett et al. showed that multimorbidity onset occurred 10–15 years earlier in people living in the most deprived areas compared with the most affluent [9].

We surmised that deprivation was likely to still have an impact on multimorbidity but that this may be secondary to the association between deprivation and age. We hypothesised that this may be due to effect measure modification (interaction) of deprivation on the association between age and multimorbidity. Plotting the distribution of deprivation and multimorbidity prevalence by age category appears to support this finding (Figure 9). Within wards of similar average age, more deprived wards have a greater prevalence of multimorbidity compared to more affluent wards. We also observe that as average age of wards increases, they generally become more skewed towards affluent wards (as shown by the vertical lines becoming generally darker as age increases).

Figure 7: Density plot of the percentage of ward population with 2 or more health conditions

Few deprived wards exist with an average age > 60 .

Due to the number of chapters and prescription measures (a total of 84 variables), the relationship between prescription variables at the BNF chapter level and multimorbidity prevalence was not visualised. These relationships were explored later in the statistical analysis. However, the relationship between total item, quantity, cost and NIC per head (across all BNF chapters) vs. prevalence was inspected. Wards with larger prescription burdens tended to have a greater multimorbidity prevalence, though a large variation between wards with similar prescription burdens can clearly be seen (Figure 10).

Finally, we inspected whether there was an association between size of ward population and multimorbidity prevalence. Figure 11 demonstrates the weak negative association observed between ward size and multimorbidity prevalence: wards with a greater population size had a lower prevalence of multimorbidity. This relationship may be explained by larger wards being urban and having a generally younger population, compared to sparsely populated wards (which are also more likely to be more rural).

The findings of the EDA strongly support the inclusion of data regarding the population structure of the ward in models to predict multimorbidity. Specifically, data regarding the population age, sex, and deprivation composition, in addition to the population of the ward, should be considered as candidate predictors, prior to consideration of prescribing patterns.

Figure 8: Univariate associations of multimorbidity

(a) Age and multimorbidity prevalence

(b) Deprivation and multimorbidity prevalence

Figure 9: The association of deprivation on multimorbidity prevalence, by age category

4 Modelling Approach 1: Regularised Linear and Random Forests Regression

In this chapter, we explore different regression modelling techniques to identify predictors of multimorbidity prevalence at an area-based level, at both the local authority and electoral ward levels, using the population as well as prescription data from 2011.

To develop a predictive regression model that can handle potentially high-dimensional prescription features, we explored two popular supervised machine learning techniques: elastic net regression and random forest regression. These methods are recognised for their effectiveness in managing high-dimensional predictors while also being able to generate interpretable insights.

4.1 Elastic Net Regression

Linear regression is one of the most used statistical modelling techniques, useful for analysing the relationship between a response variable, denoted by y_i , and a set of predictor variables, denoted by x_i (assuming a linear

Figure 10: Total prescription burden per head vs multimorbidity prevalence, by ward (2011)

Figure 11: Prevalence of multimorbidity by ward population decile

relationship exists between x_i and y_i):

$$y_i = x_i\beta + \epsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

where β is the regression coefficient that characterises the magnitude and direction of the "effect" of each predictor on the response variable, and ϵ_i is the error term. The linearity assumption comes with the benefit of making the model highly interpretable, as the coefficients provide a clear indication of how each predictor impacts the response. The unknown parameter β can be estimated using methods such as the least squares approach, which involves solving the optimisation problem:

$$\min_{\beta} \|y - X\beta\|_2^2, \quad (2)$$

where X is the matrix with i -th row given by x_i and $\|\cdot\|_k$ is the standard L_k norm. However, challenges arise when the number of predictors, p , is large and the predictors are highly correlated. This could lead to issues such as overfitting and unstable estimation. Additionally, performing variable selection could also be a challenging and time-consuming task.

In the more extreme case when $n < p$, the standard estimation approaches for linear regression become inapplicable. Regularised regression methods become useful in this context. The basic idea is to impose a suitable penalty term on the coefficients, which is added to the least square optimisation problem when fitting the model. The Lasso approach uses a L1-penalty on the coefficients, allowing coefficients of non-useful predictors to shrink to zero [20].

The ridge regression approach instead uses a L2-penalty, which is shown to be useful for handling co-linearity among predictors by shrinking the coefficients of highly correlated predictors, which leads to more stable estimation [21].

Elastic net regression exploits the ideas behind LASSO and ridge by combining the regularisation used in each approach, solving for the penalised least square problem with both types of penalties:

$$\min_{\beta} \|y - X\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda((1 - \alpha)\|\beta\|_2^2/2 + \alpha\|\beta\|_1), \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the strength of L1 or L2 penalisation and λ control the overall level of penalisation [22]. Both parameters may be regarded as tuning parameters adjusted to achieve a good balance of model fit and model complexity.

Notably, this specific penalisation method allows the elastic net to benefit advantages from both LASSO and ridge regression by performing automatic

variable selection while being able to retain important predictors even though they are highly correlated, resulting in a potentially parsimonious and more interpretable model. However, the elastic net approach may not perform optimally when features are uncorrelated, or when the number of features is much greater than the number of observations. In these cases (which are not expected in the present study) a loss of predictive power or the introduction of bias may ensue.

4.2 Random Forests

The random forest model is another popular supervised machine learning algorithm for both classification and regression (see [23] for an introduction). The fundamental building block in a random forests regression is the decision tree, which is an algorithm that recursively splits the data into increasingly smaller subsets at each node based on the value of a predictor variable, with the aim of predicting the response variable.

At each node, the algorithm selects the "best" predictor variable to split the data based on certain criteria such as information gain, or Gini loss. Once the tree is built, a prediction can be made by traversing the tree from the root node to the leaf node according to the predictor values. However, it is shown that a single decision tree is prone to overfitting. The random forest approach address this issue by using a collection of decision trees, with each tree trained on a subset of data, that is sampled with replacement. To add further randomness and reduce correlation among trees, at each node, a random subset of the features is chosen when searching for the best split.

The prediction with the random forest is obtained by aggregating (e.g. averaging) predictions generated from individual trees. Using the trained trees, feature importance can be computed as the mean and standard deviation of accumulated decrease in impurity (as measured by Gini loss) within each tree, although they are not as directly interpretable as the coefficients obtained from the elastic net regression. On the other hand, compared with (regularised) linear regression, the random forest can handle potentially highly non-linear relationships between predictors and the response variable, which can improve predictive power in certain scenarios.

4.3 Model development, training and validation

To identify key predictors of multimorbidity prevalence at an area-based level and to develop predictive models, we use and compare the regularised regression (elastic net) and the random forest approaches.

In our analysis, we considered two different area-based resolutions for the regional data: one based on the electoral ward level and another based on the coarser local authority level (obtained by aggregating data from the electoral

ward level, as above). The potential predictors under consideration include the corresponding area-based population structure parameters, including the average age and female proportion in an area, deprivation, and aggregated prescribing patterns (using BNF codes).

In our model building, population and deprivation parameters are always included as they are expected to be related to the multimorbidity prevalence based on domain knowledge [9]. Motivated by results from the exploratory data analysis, we include an interaction term between age and deprivation and for the ward level, we include the population size as a predictor.

For the aggregated prescription features, we consider information regarding the prescription of a drug from 4 different (potentially very correlated) aspects: the item count, quantity, actual cost and net ingredient cost (NIC) of the prescription (aggregated at the area and yearly level). The drugs are categorised based on the BNF (British National Formulary) code with different levels of granularity. In this analysis, we focus on three different levels of granularity for the drug classification: 2-digit (chapter only), 4-digit (chapter and section), and 6-digit (chapter, section and paragraph). Note that the 6-digit level provides very detailed information regarding a drug.

For each level of granularity, we evaluated 14 candidate models, each incorporating a subset of the four aspects of prescription information (note that when 2 or more groups of prescription features are considered, we always include either item or quantity; see Table 3). We would like to examine the relative importance and identify variables that contribute most to the prediction of multimorbidity prevalence, while also exploring the potential impact of different levels of granularity of drug data on the predictive performance of our models.

Prior to the training stage, all candidate predictors considered were standardised to have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1 (though this is not necessary for the random forest model but is performed here for consistency). For the response variable, multimorbidity prevalence, we did not perform any transformation – exploratory analysis suggests that it is reasonably normally distributed and concentrated around the mean, at both local authority and ward levels.

A key step in training the elastic net and random forest models is hyperparameter tuning. Here we adopt a grid search strategy coupled with cross-validation to optimise each model's performance. For the elastic net model, we first identify a grid of candidate value of α over the range of 0 to 1 with a grid size of 0.01. For each α , we used 10-fold cross-validation to estimate the mean squared error (MSE) and also find the optimal value of λ which minimized the MSE. By comparing the cross-validation results for different α , we identify the optimal combination that gives the lowest MSE. The final fitted elastic net model is then obtained by training with the whole data with the selected α and λ values using gradient descent, as implemented in

Table 3: Candidate Models considered for both elastic net and random forest

Candidate Model	Drug Variables Included
M1	quantity
M2	NIC
M3	item
M4	cost
M5	quantity, NIC
M6	quantity, cost
M7	quantity, item
M8	item, NIC
M9	item, cost
M10	quantity, NIC, cost
M11	quantity, NIC, item
M12	quantity, item, cost
M13	NIC, item, cost
M14	quantity, NIC, item, cost

the `glmnet` function in the `glmnet` R package [24, 25].

For the random forest algorithm, there are two hyperparameters to be selected, the number of trees (nt), and the number of predictors considered in each split nsp . A grid search strategy is employed here. For each candidate value of nt (we consider a grid from 100 to 700 with a step size of 100), nsp is optimised by minimising the out-of-bag (OOB) error using the `tuneRF` function in the `randomForest` package in R [26]. The performance of each specific combination of the hyperparameter is evaluated using a 10-fold cross-validation based on the MSE. The optimal pair was identified as the one with the lowest MSE and is used for fitting the final random forest model.

Finally, to evaluate the adequacy of the fitted model (comparing both between and within each candidate model $M1 - M14$ for the elastic net and random forest), we considered 3 different metrics: the coefficient of determination R^2 , MSE and mean absolute error (MAE). These metrics are commonly used for model evaluation and comparison in the regression context. In our implementation, they are estimated based on 10-fold cross-validation to ensure robustness.

4.4 Results

Here we present selected modelling results obtained with both the elastic net regression and random forest approaches, based on the 2011 multimorbidity and prescribing data sets, for the local authority level and the ward level.

Local authority district (LAD) level

At this level, due to the small sample size ($n = 316$), we only consider prescription granularity up to the 4-digit level. Figure 12 compares the performance of the elastic net and the random forest approaches under each feature inclusion setting, as listed in Table 3. Interestingly, we see higher R^2 values and lower MSE and MAE in all data and model scenarios for elastic net regression compared to the random forest, suggesting that the former offer a better modelling of the data. Note that in this case, the sample size is quite small, and the random forest may be more likely to suffer from overfitting.

From Figure 12 we can see that at the LAD level, incorporating additional digits (i.e. information on the section of the drug) does not yield much improvement in terms of the predictive power for either modelling approach, considering the best-performing model in each granularity. On the other hand, with the 4-digit granularity, models using different aspects of prescription information yield similar performance, suggesting that with this level of detailedness in drug data, a single feature group (e.g. either quantity/item or NIC/cost) seems to provide sufficient information for predicting the prevalence.

Focusing on the BNF 2-digit level and the elastic net regression models, M11 (quantity+item+NIC) and M12 (quantity+item+cost) are the best-performing models, suggesting that both quantity and cost information for the drug are informative at this regional level. Figure 13a shows the prediction error of each of the two fitted models, from which we see both models provide very similar and reasonably good fits. Figure 14a shows the estimated coefficients of the predictors selected by each of the 2 elastic net models, with a high agreement in the key patterns. For instance, the average age shows the strongest positive association with prevalence, followed by the quantity of cardiovascular system (BNF02) prescriptions, the item count for infections (BNF05), the quantity of gastro-intestinal system (BNF01) prescriptions, and deprivation (IMD). From the cost/NIC aspect, the respiratory system (BNF03) and nutrition and blood (BNF09) seem to be informative in predicting prevalence at the local authority level, with a significant positive association.

Figure 12: Performance comparison of elastic net regression and random forest based on the R^2 , MSE and MAE. using the BNF 2-digit (left panel) and 4-digit granularity (right panel).

Electoral ward level

At the ward level, the sample size increases significantly to $n = 4381$. We focused on the elastic net regression model given its superior performance at the local authority level and we experimented with all three levels of drug granularity up to 6-digits. Figure 15 shows the performance of different elastic net regression models that incorporate different groups of prescription features at each level of drug granularity. We can see that there seems to be a greater improvement in predictive power when transitioning from the 2-digit to the 4-digit level, compared to moving from the 4-digit to the 6-digit level, though considering the scale of the metrics the absolute improvement is small. Among the models using the BNF 4 or 6-digit granularity, the model that utilises only the item count (M3) within a prescription outperforms other candidates. This observation suggests that when using finer information on the drug, the item count appears to be the most informative aspect for predicting prevalence compared to other aspects of a prescription.

Figures 16-18 show the estimated coefficients of the identified predictors for M3 for the 2-, 4- and 6-digit levels, respectively. We can identify some common key patterns. The average age of a ward has the most predictive power out of all the variables. Other local population parameters such as decile of deprivation, ward population, and proportion of female population also exhibit strong positive effects. The interaction effect between age and

Figure 13: Predicted vs observed multimorbidity prevalence obtained from the fitted elastic net regression model M11 (left panel) and M12 (right panel). The red line is the theoretical reference line with a unit slope and a 0 intercept.

(a) Predicted vs. observed multimorbidity prevalence - model 11

(b) Predicted vs. observed multimorbidity prevalence - model 11

Figure 14: Estimated regression coefficients along with their 95% confidence bands (only non-zero coefficients are shown). Confidence intervals are estimated based on the nonparametric bootstrap method with a bootstrap sample of 1000.

(a) Elastic net regression model M11

(b) Fitted elastic net regression model M12

deprivation is also suggested from the data. With respect to the prescription variables, item counts for drugs related to the central nervous system (BNF04), cardiovascular diseases (BNF02), nutrition and blood (BNF09), and eye care (BNF11) all show positive associations with multimorbidity prevalence.

Figure 15: Performance comparison of elastic net regression models incorporating different groups of prescription features, evaluated based on R^2 , MSE, and MAE. In each panel, results for BNF 2-digit, 4-digit, and 6-digit granularity are shown in blue, red and green colours, respectively.

Figure 16: Estimated regression coefficients along with their 95% confidence bands (only non-zero coefficients are shown) for the fitted elastic net regression model M3 (with 2-digit). Confidence intervals are estimated based on the nonparametric bootstrap method with a bootstrap sample of 1000.

Figure 17: Estimated regression coefficients along with their 95% confidence bands (only non-zero coefficients are shown) for the fitted elastic net regression model M3 (with 4-digit). Confidence intervals are estimated based on the nonparametric bootstrap method with a bootstrap sample of 1000.

Figure 18: Estimated regression coefficients along with their 95% confidence bands (only non-zero coefficients are shown) for the fitted elastic net regression model M3 (with 6-digit). Confidence intervals are estimated based on the nonparametric bootstrap method with a bootstrap sample of 1000.

5 Modelling Approach 2: Bayesian Multilevel Modelling

In this section, we build on the associations observed during EDA and frequentist models in the previous section and use Bayesian multilevel modelling with population-based random effects to develop a more sophisticated understanding of the relationship between socio-demographic factors and multimorbidity prevalence.

5.1 The association of socio-demographic factors with multimorbidity

A hierarchical Bayesian linear model was used to better understand the relationship of demographic variables relationship with multimorbidity prevalence at an area-based level.

Our model is specified as:

$$y_i = \alpha_{j[i]} + \beta_{j[i]}deprivation_i * \beta_1age_i + \beta_2sex_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

where y is the prevalence of multimorbidity in a ward, *deprivation* was coded in deciles (10 = most deprived, 1 = least deprived, *sex* is the proportion of the population of a ward that is female, *age* is the mean age within a ward or LAD, j is the index of a LAD and i is the index of a ward.

A multilevel model was chosen due to the natural hierarchical structure of wards within LADs and the ability of such models to better model prevalence (provided by the intercept of the model) of areas under-represented in the available data [27].

A random coefficient was added to the deprivation index in the model given the spread of the data in relation to prevalence within a local authority area (Figure 19). The multilevel nature of the model means that instead of complete pooling of samples to estimate the intercept and coefficient for deprivation, partial pooling is used instead. Partial pooling is the use of samples (wards) within an LAD level to estimate a distribution for its parameters (intercept and coefficient for deprivation), but these distributions are generated from a 'population' parameter. This approach allows for shrinkage of the parameters. An interaction term between age and deprivation was added based on observations made during exploratory data analysis.

In Figure 19, μ_a and μ_b are population level parameters which go to the local α (intercept) and $\beta_{j[i]}$ (deprivation index coefficient). The figure is simplified and excludes the interaction term. Normal priors were given for all parameters, with μ of zero and σ of 5. These parameters were chosen to provide a proxy

Figure 19: Directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing the multilevel parameter relationship

of a null model of no effect from the coefficients and to ensure that there would be sufficient samples to help the posterior converge.

From the demographic model, simple linear models (with a single predictor) were first explored to determine the most predictive variable(s). The use of a random coefficient for the deprivation index was also evaluated. This was done via conducting Bayesian model comparison using leave-one-out (LOO) cross-validation, which is an estimate of the out-of-sample predictive fit (Figure 20). Among all the socio-demographic variables, the mean age of the population of the ward emerged as the strongest predictor of multimorbidity prevalence, followed by the proportion of the ward that was female. This analysis also supported a slight improvement associated with the use of a random coefficient, over the use of a common (complete pooling) coefficient.

Next, the complete model with and without an interaction term between age and deprivation was evaluated (Figure 21). The inclusion of an interaction term improved the model performance over the model without the interaction term.

Figure 22 shows the benefit of the partial pooling of data (orange), compared to estimating each intercept independently of other wards. An alternative approach would be to pool all wards' information and estimate a single prevalence estimate, but we would then lose information about 'clustering' at the LAD level. This partial pooling gives the benefit of both approaches, resulting in a better predictive and descriptive model.

Figure 20: Model comparison for each demographic variable using leave-one-out cross-validation. 'dep[i]' indicates random effects, compared to a common (complete pooling) 'dep' coefficient

Figure 21: Model comparison between one with interaction vs without, the use of "*" indicates interaction between age and deprivation index

5.2 Including Practice Level Prescribing Data in the multilevel model

The multilevel model above was expanded to include prescription data. For this purpose, output from the elastic net cross-validation was used to inform which prescription information to include in the model. Prescription items, recorded at the 4-digit BNF level (chapter and section) was used. Given computational limitations, only the 100 most frequently prescribed BNF items were investigated with the model.

Figure 22: Estimating multimorbidity using the multilevel model (orange) vs. a model in which each LAD mean was estimated independently (blue)

The prescribing variables were modelled as predictors using the same priors in μ and σ . Following the fit of the model, LOO cross-validation was computed and indicated that the addition of the prescribing data did not yield a major improvement to overall model performance.

Exploration of the coefficients of the 4-digit BNF items demonstrated a number of significant associations (items for which the highest posterior density interval did not include zero). These included drugs used to treat hypertension and heart failure, diabetes, in addition to drugs affecting bone metabolism.

6 Exploring the suitability of the data for model-based forecasting

Although prescription and population data were successfully pre-processed for the period 2011 - 2022, due to numerous changes at the ward level, we were not able to use our models for the purposes of forecasting multimorbidity. In this section, we will explore – with illustrative examples – why we believe that these data are not suitable for this purpose in their current form, and will discuss strategies that could be used to overcome the issues encountered going forward.

In addition, in order to demonstrate that the EPD and PLPD can be successfully compared, we selected two wards in Newcastle Upon Tyne to explore. Prescription data is available for up to 2022, whereas population data is only available up to 2020. As Covid-19 began to significantly impact the United Kingdom during 2020, we decided to focus on 2019 as we would expect prescription patterns to be impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic.

6.1 Selecting wards

We wanted to compare the extremes of deprivation decile and multimorbidity prevalence. Initially, we decided to choose Byker and North Jesmond as Byker has a Carstairs deprivation decile of 10 and a multimorbidity prevalence of 23.5%, whereas North Jesmond has a Carstairs deprivation decile of 1 and a multimorbidity of 10.8%. However, we noted major differences in prescribing activity in Byker between 2013 and 2014 (Figure 23). Using the data available for Byker and surrounding wards (and data regarding GP surgeries in England), we concluded that consolidation of a number of GP surgeries *outside* the ward to a location *within* Byker is responsible for the increase (Figure 24). This illustrates some issues with the use of 2011 ward as the unit of analysis and suggests that a higher-level geography (or a means of apportioning prescriptions to a small-level geography using GP registration data) may be preferable.

Therefore, we made the decision to change to a ward with a greater burden of deprivation but greater stability of prescribing behaviour. Walker has a total population comparable to North Jesmond, has a deprivation decile of 10, and a multimorbidity prevalence of 24.8%, making it a suitable choice. The average age, however, is interestingly higher in Walker than in North Jesmond and this could be a contributing factor towards a higher multimorbidity prevalence in Walker compared to North Jesmond (Table 4).

Figure 23: The total NIC cost for Byker differs significantly for 2011-2013 (based on 2011 wards and ELPD data) and 2014 onwards (based on 2021 wards and EPD data).

Table 4: Comparison of selected wards in 2011 and 2019

Measure	North Jesmond	Byker	Walker
Ward code 2011	E05001103	E05001091	E05001108
Ward code 2019	E05011454	E05011439	E05011458
Population estimate 2011	10,722	12,154	11,662
Proportion female 2011	46.7%	50%	51.4%
Average age 2011	30	37	37
Population estimate 2019	10,359	11,885	11,772
Proportion female 2019	49.3%	48.2%	52.7%
Average age 2019	30	37	38
Deprivation decile	1	10	10
Multimorbidity prevalence	10.8%	23.5%	24.8%

6.2 Prescription changes in North Jesmond and Walker, 2011 - 2019

We began by looking at the total NIC per person for each BNF chapter in 2011. For most BNF chapters, total NIC per person was higher in Walker than in North Jesmond (see figure 25), which may have been expected as Walker is a more deprived area with a higher multimorbidity prevalence. One interesting reverse

Figure 24: The total NIC cost for all prescriptions allocated to the Byker, Walker and Walkergate wards appears to be more consistent over time

in this trend is BNF chapter 19 which contains other drugs and preparations and therefore likely represents an expensive niche drug which was prescribed for only one or two people. This is supported when looking at the total items prescribed per chapter.

The three BNF chapters which had the greatest spend per person in both wards were BNF02 (cardiovascular system-related drugs), BNF03 (respiratory system-related drugs), and BNF04 (central nervous system [CNS]-related drugs, including analgesics). The conditions included in the definition of multimorbidity by Barnett *et al.* included a number of chronic cardiovascular, respiratory and neurological conditions (in addition to chronic painful conditions), and therefore higher utilisation of drugs treating these systems would be expected in a region with greater multimorbidity prevalence [9].

The per person NIC in 2011 was highest in the BNF chapter related to the CNS (BNF04), which included drugs such as anti-depressants and analgesics. The associated cost in Walker (around £80 per person) was approximately double that of North Jesmond (£40 per person).

In 2019, there was a higher NIC per person for all BNF chapters in Walker compared to North Jesmond (Figure 26). The chapter with the highest NIC per person remains CNS-related drugs in North Jesmond in 2019, however there was a change to respiratory system-related drugs in Walker. There is a striking

Figure 25: Annual NIC per person by BNF chapter in North Jesmond and Walker: 2011

Figure 26: Annual NIC per person by BNF chapter in North Jesmond and Walker: 2019

change in maximum NIC between 2011 and 2019. In 2011 the maximum NIC was around £80 per person, whereas in 2019 it is only around £45 per person.

This likely reflects greater availability of generic versions of drugs, which has led to cost reductions.

Focusing on North Jesmond, there is a higher number of prescriptions per person in 2019 for the majority of BNF chapters, in comparison to 2011 (Figure 27a). BNF02 and BNF04 are the most prescribed chapters in North Jesmond, which is reflected in the 2011 and 2019 NIC data (Figures 25 and 26). The BNF chapters which saw a reduced number of drugs prescribed from 2011 to 2019 include BNF05, BNF13, BNF14 and BNF20 which are drugs covering infections, skin, immunological products and vaccines, and dressings, respectively. There has been a campaign to reduce the non-evidence-based use of broad spectrum antibiotics in recent years due to the emerging threat of antibiotic resistant microorganisms. Therefore, it is logical that drugs which fall into the infections chapter would be reduced per person, between 2011 and 2019. Other items for which prescriptions were observed to reduce from 2011 to 2019 were those available on an “over the counter” basis.

We further looked into which sections of BNF02 and BNF04 are the most commonly prescribed in North Jesmond. Antihypertensives (BNF0205) and lipid-lowering therapies (BNF0212) were the most common drugs prescribed related to the Cardiovascular System, whereas antidepressants (BNF0403) and analgesics (BNF0407) were the two most common types of drugs prescribed related to the CNS (Figure 27b). All of these drugs can be used to treat diseases which are considered to form part of the range of multimorbid diseases (Table 1).

When looking at Walker, broadly the same trends were observed as in North Jesmond (Figure 28a). Drugs targeting the cardiovascular System and CNS were the most prominent drugs prescribed in both 2011 and 2019 (Figure 28b). Additionally, the most common drug types prescribed in both those chapters were hypertension and heart failure drugs (BNF0205), cholesterol-regulating drugs (BNF0205), antidepressants (BNF0403) and analgesics (BNF0407) (Figure 28b).

Although both wards show the same trends in drugs prescribed, the absolute number of prescription is much higher in the more deprived ward (Walker). For example, people in North Jesmond were prescribed four drugs relating to the cardiovascular System (BNF02) in 2011 and five in 2019, on average. In Walker, the average person was prescribed 13 drugs relating to the cardiovascular system in 2011 and 15 in 2019. Similar trends were seen with drugs relating to the CNS.

Through analyses at the ward level, we have identified important and explainable trends (both between extremes of deprivation status, and over time). However, such analysis is not possible to scale to the entirety of the wards of England, due to the issues highlighted with changing ward boundaries and the dynamic nature of the availability of GP surgeries within

Figure 27: Changes in number of items prescribed per person annually in North Jesmond, Newcastle Upon Tyne: 2011 to 2019

(a) BNF chapters

(b) Sections of BNF02 and BNF04

Figure 28: Changes in number of items prescribed per person annually in Walker, Newcastle Upon Tyne: 2011 to 2019.

(a) BNF chapters

(b) Sections of BNF02 and BNF04

an area. If these issues surrounding the geospatial nature of the data could be resolved and all wards could be compared then this could help gain insight into disease prevalence and drug prescriptions at a national level.

7 Conclusions and future work

7.1 Apportioning prescription data to geographic areas

Our approach to assign prescription data to 2011 electoral wards was necessarily naïve, due to the time constraints and computational resources available during the one-week data study group. We recognise that this was a strong assumption that does not reflect the reality of GP surgery registration patterns. In addition, this led to the exclusion of approximately 40% of wards during subsequent analysis. Changing to the next highest level of geography (local authority districts) was considered, but led to marked loss of granularity and incurred the $p > n$ problem (where the number of potential predictors, p , are greater than the number of observations, n), as described above. A more sophisticated method of apportioning prescribing data to small areas of geography would ideally have been used. We are aware that NHS Digital have published counts of patients registered at each GP surgery in England, at Lower Super Output Area (LSOA), since 2013. Although not applicable to our 2011 data, we envisage that these data information could be used to apportion prescriptions from each GP surgery by the proportion of registered from each LSOA (which could then be aggregated up to a more analytically appropriate Middle Super Output Area (MSOA) level. This approach would overcome the limitations associated with our simplistic attribution of prescriptions to the ward in which the GP surgery was located in future analyses of this nature.

An alternative approach for the 2011 data would be to specify a radius from every GP surgery. The longitude/latitude of each GP surgery may be estimated from its postcode. The centroid of each ward is also available. These can be used to calculate the Euclidean distance between every surgery/ward pair. The distance from each GP surgery to the ward centroid could be used as a weighting to allocate prescriptions from every English surgery to each ward. A penalty term (such as $1/n$) could be applied to penalise long distance travel. A normalising factor would be required to ensure the marginal number of prescriptions allocated to wards was equal to the total number prescribed by local GP surgeries. This approach avoids developing assumptions for the maximum distance an individual will travel to see a GP or the number of closest surgeries allocated to a ward. The inverse distance measure could be tuned as a hyper-parameter. Such an approach could be applied to the 2011 data.

7.2 Further model development

We explored elastic net, random forest and multilevel modelling approaches using features derived from population parameters and prescription data for predicting the multimorbidity prevalence at an area level. The prescription data is complex and high-dimensional. In our current models, we utilised prescription features that included item count, quantity, cost, and net ingredient cost for each drug category, ranging from 2 to 6-digit BNF granularity. However, we feel that there is significant scope for further feature engineering in order to improving the performance and predictive ability of models.

For instance, the correlations between prescription features could be further explored using models and learners that can capture the complex relationships that exist among them. Such an approach could capture combinations of drugs prescribed by a GP surgery more often than expected, suggesting the possibility of a greater burden of multimorbidity managed by the practice. An alternative idea along the lines of exploring drug prescription patterns would be to explore the diversity of drug prescriptions at the regional level. For example, Shannon diversity could be used to investigate this pattern. The Shannon index, H , is an information statistic that measures the average diversity of a sample (in this context, in terms of numbers of different prescriptions). This is motivated by the relationship between polypharmacy and multimorbidity: a more diverse prescription pattern (involving a variety of drug groups) may be associated with a higher burden of multimorbidity in an area.

A Bayesian network (or any other network) approach can also be applied to explore the relationship between drugs. Both multimorbidity prevalence and individual condition prevalence data could be incorporated into such a network to elucidate patterns of prescription and diagnosis. Additional variables that are potentially related to multimorbidity prevalence, such as environmental factors and healthcare utilisation, could also be linked and incorporated into the analysis.

There remains scope for further model exploration and improvement. It would be interesting to assess the performance of the random forest algorithm at the ward level. We did not experiment further during this DSG because it was computationally expensive to train, and the elastic net provided a reasonable fit to the data at both ward and LAD level. However, the predictive performance of the random forest may be improved by leveraging more data at the ward level.

In addition, our exploratory data analysis reveals high variability in terms of population size at either the local authority/ward level. In our current analysis, each training data point is assigned an equal weight (i.e. treated as equally important). However, it may be reasonable to expect that information from areas with much larger population sizes should have a larger contribution to

the model fit compared to areas with much smaller populations. To address this issue, we could consider using a weighted (according to *e.g.* population size) version of the elastic net or random forest to better account for this variability across different areas.

The current Bayesian multilevel model was built naïvely for quick exploration and testing of several different model forms. Should this model be explored further, a different prior could be used for specific coefficients in order to ensure positivity, such as an exponential distribution. L1-regularisation could also be explored for the prescription variables in order to tune the dimensionality of the resulting model. This could be done using a Laplace distribution for the coefficient. Alternatively, a “spike and slab” hyper-prior could be explored as a mechanism of feature selection.

An alternative to the Bayesian multilevel model would be a Gaussian process (GP) model to model the geospatial data. A GP model would capture the information from spatially neighbouring areas, which could be important in this context.

7.3 Longitudinal prediction and analysis

With the developed predictive model, our next goal would be to forecast changes in multimorbidity prevalence across different geographical areas in England, between 2012 and 2022. By examining these predictions, we can identify how multimorbidity prevalence changed over time in different geographical areas in England and identify which areas experienced the most significant increase (or decrease).

At a more detailed level, we could investigate the potential reasons for such increased prevalence: *e.g.*, is it associated with factors such as increased average age in that ward, a higher deprivation decile value, or other environmental or historical factors such as being near to high pollution locations, receding heavy industry, coastal locations or as a result of depopulation. It would also be very interesting to focus on the period during and after March-2020 (The Covid-19 era) to see if there are any notable changes or new patterns emerging in multimorbidity prevalence.

8 Data Study Group Team Members

8.1 Challenge Leaders

Jonathan Batty (Principal Investigator) is a Wellcome Trust Clinical PhD Fellow at the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA), University of Leeds. His research is focused on the interaction of multimorbidity and cardiovascular disease, with a specific focus on myocardial infarction.

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8.2 Data Study Group Participants

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